

GREEN NANOCOMPOSITE FROM BIODEGRADABLE POLYMER AND ORGANICALLY MODIFIED CLAY

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ABSTRACT

Green nanocomposites are the wave of the future and considered as the next generation of materials. Biopolymers are now moving into the mainstream and the polymers that are biodegradable or based on renewable “feedstock” may soon be competing with commodity plastics. To find new applications of biopolymers through innovation technology is a formidable task for scientists. One of the most promising ways in improving the properties of biopolymers is through nanotechnology. Polymer nanocomposites – generally a polymer containing modified nanoclay additives -- have been used commercially for a few years in niche applications. Nanocomposites are lighter than metals and filled composites - - a strong motivation for significant fuel and energy savings in transportation. Polymer clay nanocomposites especially polypropylene (PP)/Thermoplastic polyolefin (TPO)/Nylon based nanocomposites are under consideration by automakers. True nanocomposites exhibit improved stiffness/strength without sacrificing toughness and exhibit reduced gas permeability (improved barrier properties), a lower coefficient of thermal expansion and an improved heat deflection temperature. There is also a growing urgency to develop novel biobased products and innovative technologies that can reduce the US dependence on fossil fuel and save our precious environment. Green/biobased nanocomposites can be the next generation of materials. Renewable resource-based biodegradable polymers including cellulosic plastic (plastic made from tree/wood cellulose), polylactic acid (PLA – a corn-derived plastic) and polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHA – a bacterial polyester) are some the potential biopolymers which with effective nanoclay reinforcement can be the “green” nanocomposites for automotive applications and packaging applications. However green nanocomposites need to be “sustainable” to compete with existing petroleum-based polymer clay nanocomposites. Green nanocomposites derived from renewable resources, having recyclability and ‘triggered’ biodegradability (i.e. stable until ‘triggered’ to degrade) coupled with commercial viability and environmental acceptability are termed “sustainable”.

KEY WORDS: Green nanocomposites, Biodegradable polymer, clay, Cellulosic bioplastics, Automotive applications, Biocomposites, Packaging Applications.

INTRODUCTION AND MOTIVATION

Polymer nanocomposites open a new dimension for plastics and composites¹. New and improved materials have been and will continue to be a fundamental way that we define our advancement as a society. Major changes in automobile propulsion will be coming in the 21st century, and materials will be a key enabling technology². The high expectations for greater fuel economy and lower emissions are creating a demand for new low-cost and high-performance lightweight materials for structural applications. Nanocomposites are a novel class of new

composite materials exhibiting superior mechanical, thermal, and processing properties, suitable for structural applications in automotive and other applications^{3,4}. A combination of customer

Figure 1: *Biopolymers Classification: From Renewable Resources/Petroleum/Biomass & Petroleum mixed Resources*

expectations, environmental stewardship, and tightened regulations will lead to more use of eco-friendly materials. Published reports have shown³ that nanocomposite plastic parts offer a 25% weight savings on average over highly filled plastics and as much as 80% over steel. Since about 90% of the total energy⁵ used by an automobile during its life cycle is from fuel consumed, this reduction in weight offers potential of significant energy savings. Nanocomposite-based parts provide stiffness, strength, and reliability comparable to other materials. Besides weight and energy savings,

nanocomposites also offer enhanced strength and modulus, corrosion resistance, noise dampening, dimensional stability and thermal stability.

Nano reinforcement of bio-based polymers are poised to create the next generation of value-added novel *eco*-friendly nanocomposites in the 21st century. The opportunities are clear; however several challenges need to be addressed through innovative research and development. European Union (EU-15), Japan and United States (US) are striving to design and engineer environmentally benign materials (EBM) to replace/substitute for existing petroleum-based materials. Overall, in the use of environmentally benign manufacturing including technologies, applications, and policies, the US ranks third behind Europe and Japan⁶. The US Biomass Research and Development Act of 2000 has brought together the US Department of Agriculture (USDA) along with the US Department of Energy (DOE) to promote biobased products. Presidential executive order 13134 calls for tripling America’s use of biobased and bioenergy products by 2010. Executive order 13149 calls for a 20% reduction in federal vehicular use of petroleum by 2005. The recent “FARM BILL” signed by President Bush into law on May 13, 2002 also encourages bio-based product use in the USA.

Currently, there is a considerable interest in biodegradable polymers, which can be used as alternatives to traditional plastics, thus reducing the pollution caused by plastic wastes. Significant amounts and varieties of plastics, notably polyolefins, polystyrene, and poly (vinyl chloride) are currently produced from fossil fuels, consumed and discarded into the environment, ending up as nondegradable wastes. Their incineration produces carbon dioxide and in some cases, toxic gases, and contributes to global pollution. Industrial ecology, eco-efficiency and green chemistry/engineering will be the guides for the next generation of products and processes. Bio-based polymers are now moving into the mainstream and the

Figure 2: *Schematic representations - - Value-added Materials from bio-based/biodegradable polymers through Composites, Blending and Nanocomposites for applications in Automotives, Computer housing, Agricultural tools, Consumer goods and Packaging*

polymers that are biodegradable or based on renewable “feedstock” may soon be competing with commodity plastics. To find new applications of biopolymers through innovative technology is a formidable task for engineers.

Figure 3: Structures of possible morphologies when processing organo-clay with polymers

Green nanocomposites are considered as the next generation of materials. U.S. Government’s National Nanotechnology Initiative (NNI)⁷ will lead to the next industrial revolution. President Bush’s FY 2003 budget of \$710 million calls for an increased federal investment in nanotechnology. The European Commission (EC) stands to pledge up to 1.2 billion euros (US\$1.2) over the next four years to establish nanotech research networks⁸. Experts predict that nanotechnology will grow to a \$1 trillion business in the next 10 to 15 years, with nanomaterials playing a

prominent role.

VALUE-ADDED APPLICATIONS FOR BIO-BASED POLYMERS

Biopolymers may be derived/made from bio-resources like corn, wood cellulose etc. or can also be made from petroleum sources or may be obtained from mixed sources of biomass and petroleum (Fig.1). The best-known petroleum-derived biodegradable biopolymers are aliphatic/aliphatic-aromatic copolyesters like Easter Bio® from Eastman Chemical Co.; Biomax® from DuPont; Ecoflex® from BASF and Bionolle® from Showa HighPolymer. Biopolymers from renewable resources are attracting much attention because of their biomass origin and their zero net carbon dioxide impact on the environment in contrast to the petroleum-based biodegradable polymers. Poly Lactic Acid or polylactides (PLA) recently gained much attention recently because of its origin from corn. Cargill Dow Polymers LLC (CDC) opened the world’s 1st commercial-scale PLA plant in Nebraska in 2002. Their \$300 million plant is producing 300 million-lb. /year

Figure 4: Various factors in combination provide “Synergism” in designing high performance Green Nanocomposites

Figure 5: Nanocomposite process diagram for automotive applications (ref.2)

of PLA. The renewable resource based PLA polymers are competing with petroleum-derived non-biodegradable plastics from a sustainability⁹ perspective as well. Among all the

biodegradable polymers; starch plastics are comparatively low cost but their applications are mostly concentrated on disposable items and packaging. High water absorption behavior of starch plastics limits their application ranges. Cellulose esters in the form of cellulose acetate (CA), Cellulose acetate butyrate (CAB) and Cellulose acetate propionate (CAP) are commercial

Figure 6: Mechanism for improved barrier properties

biopolymers from Eastman Chemical Co. Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are bacterial derived bioplastics and recently have attracted much attention. Polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB) is the 1st bacterial polyester in the PHA family. The copolymer, Poly (hydroxybutyrate-co-valerate) or (PHBV) has also been developed for specific applications. The biopolymers of the PHA family can be used in applications like shampoo bottles and packaging; however their high costs have restricted such applications. Companies such as Metabolix and Procter & Gamble (P&G) are quite active in bringing PHAs to the commercial market¹⁰. Metabolix hopes to produce PHAs at a of ~\$1/lb. P&G is investigating the manufacture of branched bacterial polyester (Nodax®) and hopes to reduce Nodax® prices to \$0.45 to \$1/ lb. Yet another type of biopolymers can be derived from combining bio- and petroleum based sources. The best example of such a biopolymer is Sorona® from DuPont. This bio-based polymer is

an analog of Poly ethylene terephthalate (PET). The glycol (1,3 propanediol) used in making Sorona® is derived from renewable rather than from petroleum sources. Thus Sorona® is a 3-carbon glycol terephthalate (3-GT) polymer allowing bio-based polyurethanes to be made from bio-derived polyol and petroleum derived isocyanates and bio-based polyesters to be derived from a blend of petroleum derived unsaturated polyester resin and derivitized vegetable oil.

Figure 7: Cellulose ester Powder from Tree (wood pulp) in powder form

Most of the commercial biodegradable polymers cost ~\$2/ pound vs. \$0.4-0.5/pound for traditional thermoplastics¹¹. The wide spread use of petroleum derived traditional plastics is the result of several years of research in finding applications which require large-scale production and thus helped in bringing down their costs to the present levels. Bio-based and/or biodegradable polymers are recent developments emerging because of the growing environmental awareness. More value can be added to bio-based polymers through: (i) blending (ii) composites and (iii) Nanocomposites (Fig.2).

NANO REINFORCEMENTS OF BIO-BASED POLYMERS

Nano reinforcement of bio-based polymers offer a unique route to designing eco-friendly green nanocomposites for several applications. A fairly new area of materials has emerged in which the reinforcing material has dimensions of approximately one billionth of a meter, or one nanometer. A composite material made by reinforcing a polymeric matrix with nanoreinforcement is called a nanocomposite. As a result of “nano-scale” dispersion of these high aspect ratio and high surface area nanoreinforcements, even at very low level concentrations of up to 5 wt%, the reinforcement efficiency of nanocomposites can be significantly better than the conventional mineral fillers. A conventional glass fiber has a modulus of ~ 72 GPa vs. ~ 172 GPa for nano-clay. Various nano reinforcements currently coming-up are nano clays, cellulose nanowhiskers, ultrafine titanium dioxide, nanographite and carbon nanotubes. Carbon Nanotube based polymer composites are poised to exhibit exceptional mechanical, thermal and electrical properties. As reported¹³ elastic modulus for carbon nanotubes exceeds 1 TPa (1000 GPa). However, carbon nanotube global production in 2000 was only 1 to 5 Kg, at a cost of \$300 to 1500/g¹².

Currently, the most heavily researched type of nanocomposite uses layered mineral clays (typical clay is montmorillonite) as the reinforcing phase. Montmorillonite is hydrophilic which makes proper exfoliation and dispersion into the polymers difficult. Thus, montmorillonite is usually modified through substitution of sodium ions with organic onium ions (intercalation). Such chemical modification expands the clay gallery and thus creates a material which can be

Figure 8: Storage modulus variation with T of cellulose acetate and its nanocomposite

more easily be dispersed into a polymer matrix. Three ways of processing nanocomposites are: (i) Solution technique (ii) In-situ polymerization and (iii) Melt compounding. Melt compounding would have the highest potential for commercialization. Fig.3 depicts the possible morphologies to be developed during processing of polymer-clay nanocomposites. Biopolymers need to be modified (formulated) to make them suitable for use as matrix polymers in nanocomposites. The adhesion between clay and biopolymer as well as effective dispersion through optimized processing is essential. The use of a proper coupling agent improves the clay-polymer matrix adhesion. The extent of intercalation and exfoliation of nano clays in biopolymer matrix affects the performance of the resulting nanocomposites. These factors need to act synergistically in order to produce a high performance green nanocomposites (Fig. 4).

NONBIODEGRADABLE POLYMER-CLAY BASED NANOCOMPOSITES vs. BIOPOLYMER-CLAY BASED GREEN NANOCOMPOSITES

The value-added application ranges of biodegradable polymers/biopolymers in automotives, packaging and consumer goods are represented schematically in Fig. 2. The misconception that biopolymers cannot be stable in long-life applications needs to be addressed. Through proper functionalization/modifications; most biopolymers can be used for structural applications. Nanocomposites may be produced by incorporating nanometer-sized clay particles in polymers such as polypropylene (PP), polyethylene (PE), polyesters, and epoxies etc.¹⁴⁻¹⁷. The 1st practical example of polymeric nanocomposites for automotive applications was nylon 6 – clay hybrid (NCH) used to make a timing-belt cover by the Toyota Motor Company. The tensile modulus of NCH is twice that of nylon 6 (2.1 vs. 1.1 GPa) and the coefficient of linear thermal expansion is reduced to half (6.3×10^{-5} vs. 13×10^{-5}) for a NCH containing only 1.6 vol.-% clay mineral¹⁸. Figure 5 illustrates the key steps of the conceptual process needed to produce nanocomposites for automotive applications³. Polypropylene, which includes a family of enhanced reactor-grade thermoplastic olefins (TPOs) as well as compounded grades, offers an innovative material solution for a number of automotive applications. PP-clay hybrid composites have been prepared at Toyota Central R&D via melt intercalation of organo-clay with PP modified with maleic anhydride.

Figure 9: (a) ESEM of organically modified clay (b) Bright field TEM of the microscale morphology showing a uniform distribution of particles, (c) Bright field TEM showing mesoscale features of clay particles oriented perpendicular (A) and parallel (B) to the electron beam. Note: TEM (b) and (c) correspond to green nanocomposites of CA with 5% of organo clay)

or hydroxy groups^{19,20}. Although PP has sufficient tensile and flexural properties, its low impact strength, necessitated the invention of high impact PP - - known as extended PP or TPO through the incorporation of an elastomeric component. Such rubberized PP or TPO sacrifices the flexural and tensile properties of virgin polypropylene. General Motors (GM) recently launched²¹ a production part, “step-assist” for 2002 GMC Safari - - as the first exterior application of a TPO-based nanocomposite. This is a significant 1st step since it implies that more applications for nanocomposites will be forthcoming in future vehicles. However, since both PP and TPO are non-biodegradable petro-based polymers - - the OEMs (Original Equipment Manufacturers) are looking for alternative eco-friendly green materials. Researchers are looking to produce controlled biodegradable nanocomposite materials to supplement/replace PP/TPO-based nanocomposites. Biopolymers reinforced with suitably modified organo-clays could produce green nanocomposites.

PLA/layered silicate nanocomposites have been prepared²² successfully through melt extrusion of PLA and organically modified clay. These nanocomposites exhibited improved materials properties compared to the PLA matrix without clay. In a recent publication²³ it is reported that biodegradability of neat PLA increased significantly with reinforcement of specific

organically modified clay. Green nanocomposites also would find many applications in the packaging area. Nanoreinforcements create a torturous path reducing the diffusion of various gases and water vapor thus producing high barrier properties (Fig. 6) in nanocomposites making them of immense interest for packaging applications.

In on-going research at Michigan State University, green nanocomposites from cellulose ester bioplastics and nano-clays are being investigated as a ‘green’ substitute for PP/TPO-clay based nanocomposites for automotive parts. Cellulose esters are thermoplastic materials produced through esterification of cellulose obtained from trees (Fig.7). The cellulose acetates produced have mainly been in the form of white powders. Such cellulose acetate powders in the presence of phthalate plasticizer and other additives are extruded to produce various grades of commercial cellulosic plastics in granulated form. In our experiments²⁴ organically modified montmorillonite commercial clay was pre-blended mechanically with cellulose acetate and liquid plasticizer. The whole mixture was then extruded to obtain a thermoformable-extruded sheet, which was compression molded into test specimens. The storage modulus variation with temperature (Fig.8)

Figure 10: *Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) approach*

of the plasticized cellulose acetate (30% citrate plasticizer) and its nanocomposites (reinforced with 5% organically modified clay) exhibit encouraging results - - most notably at reduced temperature (-90°C) the modulus of green nanocomposites increases by ~50% while at higher temperature the improvement of modulus is ~84%. Environmental scanning microscopy (ESEM) of as received clay and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) studies of our green nanocomposites are presented in Fig.9. The bright field TEM micrograph shows the mesoscale morphology of cellulose plastic – clay green nanocomposites. Layer expansion varies within the primary particle and crystallites. An increase of plasticizer content in the cellulose ester plastic formulation improves the impact strength and percent elongation while showed a decreasing trend in tensile strength and modulus values²⁵. Processing also affects the physico-mechanical and thermal properties of cellulosic bio-plastics. Research is continuing into the optimum formulation

of cellulose ester plastic, different processes including extrusion followed by injection molding, use of alternative organo-clay compositions and use of certain coupling agents to produce viable green nanocomposites. As discussed earlier; although biopolymers are emerging as alternatives to existing petroleum-derived plastics, the present low levels of production and high costs restrict their widespread applications. Although biopolymers can compete with existing polymers on a performance bases, new applications for biopolymers would stimulate large scale productions of biopolymers to attain sustainability and eco-friendliness.

By reducing the energy and materials required to provide goods and services, nanotechnology has the potential to improve economic efficiency while improving environmental performance and sustainability. Life cycle assessment (LCA) of 'green' nanocomposites materials needs to be completed in order to achieve commercialization. Fig. 10 represents a simplified life cycle for the stages of green nanocomposites and conventional nanocomposites. The total environmental/economical impacts need to be studied to prove the industrial and environmental potential of nanocomposites for automotive applications.

CONCLUSIONS

New environmental regulations, societal concerns, and growing environmental awareness have stimulated the search for new products and processes that are compatible with the environment. The recent EU's end of vehicle life directive makes car manufacturers responsible for recycling cars at the end of their working lives for new vehicles by 2002 and all cars in 2007. A minimum amount of recycled plastics (~5 to 10 wt.%) of the total weight of a car seems to be a goal for the near future. It is also reported that in certain cases "recycled plastics" cost more than "virgin plastic" and show inferior performance. 'Green' plastics offer a practical solution to automakers beyond recycling. True 'green' nanocomposites would exhibit improved strength and stiffness with little sacrifice of toughness and reduced gas/water vapor permeability, lower coefficient of expansion and improved heat deflection temperature. Demands for superior fuel economy along with the current green movement open-up an immense opportunity for the use of new, high performance, light weight green nanocomposite materials. About 100 lbs. of plastic have been added to the average new car over the past 10 years, displacing 200-300 lbs. of other materials²⁶. In North America the market potential for plastic body panels is estimated at 1 billion lbs./year, and globally at 3 billion lbs/year. Biopolymers are now entering the commercial market and have a strong potential to replace/substitute the usual petroleum-derived plastics both on cost and performance basis. The newly developing green nanocomposites can compete with the existing petroleum polymer-clay based nanocomposites in greener automotive parts and green packaging materials applications. Such increased use would insure the sustainability of 'green' nanocomposites and pose exciting opportunities for real world applications in the 21st century materials world.

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